

NON-LINEAR MODELLING OF RESIDUAL STRESS DEVELOPMENT IN A GRP FLANGE

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SUMMARY: The magnitude and distribution of residual stresses in a GRP flange of 50mm internal diameter were investigated numerically using the finite element method (FEM). The analysis includes a comparison between numerical simulations of a flange that was manufactured using the commonly used stage lamination method. Linear simulations considered the effects of stage lamination, chemically-based cure shrinkage and thermal shrinkage. Non-linear analyses considered the effects of creep relief of residual stresses. All analyses were carried out using experimentally obtained material properties. A comparison of numerical results was made with experimental results from Whitfield [1]. It was found that the spring back could not be accurately predicted with either linear or non-linear analysis. Further work using non-linear techniques that take account of micro-scale stresses is required.

KEYWORDS: Residual Stress, Creep, Stress Relaxation, Vinyl Ester, FEM, Non-Linear, Stage Lamination, Cure Cycles, GFRP, CSM

INTRODUCTION

Residual stresses in glass fibre reinforced plastic (GFRP) composites develop due to chemical and thermal volume changes in the polymeric material during manufacture. These stresses can result in deformation, as well as micro-failures such as cracks and fibre buckling. This sometimes leads to premature failure of products made from this material [2]. A pipe flange is one example where such effects are clearly seen. Residual stresses that develop within the flange cause the face to deflect into a convex surface after the flange is post-cured [3,4]. This effect is known as spring-back and prevents the flange from being fitted properly. One way of achieving a proper fit is to grind the flange face flat. This has the disadvantage of exposing the reinforcing fibres to the environment. Another way is to force the convex surface back to its original position by using clamping bolts. The resulting set of stresses from this operation can promote environmentally assisted cracking in the flange [5]. Since components made from GFRP such as flanges and pipes are being used increasingly in the chemical industry due to their inherent corrosion resistance, it is important to be able to model the development of residual stresses within these components.

Each of the manufacturing stages contributes towards the development of residual stresses. The first of these stages is the initial cure shrinkage which is not significant since most of the volume change occurs prior to polymer gelation where the polymer is a fluid. The second and the more significant stage is the post-cure process. Whitfield [1] has shown that strain changes in a chopped strand mat (CSM) laminate are 10 times larger after post-cure when compared to strain changes after initial cure. These strains result from additional matrix

shrinkage at elevated temperatures. It is widely accepted that residual stresses due to post-cure arise during cool-down from the post-cure temperature [6]. The reason for this is the large difference in the coefficients of thermal expansion of the polymeric material and the reinforcing fibres.

Additional stresses arise from the use of stage lamination. Due to the large thickness of GFRP flanges, they are usually fabricated using a process where each successive layer is placed on a layer that has already cured. This ensures that thick sections do not build up excessive heat (“exotherm”) during curing. The initial layers are, however, partially post-cured by the heat generated from the exothermic cure reactions of subsequent layers. This results in unsymmetrical post-cure shrinkage through the thickness of the laminate, which in turn results in additional residual stress build-up.

This work is an extension on previous work by Whitfield [1], in which the spring back of GFRP pipe flanges was examined by means of experimental and analytical techniques. It was found that a conventional linear finite element analysis is unable to predict the experimentally measured spring back of pipe flanges. However, Whitfield [1] used linear, orthotropic, temperature dependent elements with a very coarse mesh. His model also assumed that material properties around the flange corner varied at three discrete angles between 90° (upper tube section) and 0° (flat section). It was decided to re-evaluate the linear analysis using a finer mesh made up of non-linear elements, whose mechanical properties vary continuously around the corner. Whitfield [1] conjectured that non-linear effects such as creep and unsymmetrical post-cure shrinkage due to stage lamination must be significant contributors to the development of residual stress and the associated deformations. The aim of this work is to evaluate this hypothesis.

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION

An experimental investigation was previously carried out by Whitfield [1], based on three 50mm internal diameter pipe flanges fabricated in accordance with British Standard [7]. The flanges were laid up by hand using chopped strand mat and Derakane 411-350 vinyl ester resin. Spring back of the pipe flange was measured between the inner and outer circumference of the flange face. Material properties were experimentally determined and are shown in Table. 1

Table 1: Physical material properties as determined by Whitfield [1]

Young's modulus (GPa)		Poisson's ratio		Shear modulus (GPa)		Cure shrinkage ($\mu\epsilon$)		Post-cure shrinkage ($\mu\epsilon$)		Coefficient of thermal expansion ($\mu\epsilon/^\circ\text{C}$)	
E_x	9.67	ν_{xy}	0.34	G_{xy}	3.62	S_x	94	S_x	938	CTE_x	26.72
E_y	9.67	ν_{xz}	0.39	G_{xz}	1.99	S_y	94	S_y	938	CTE_y	26.72
E_z	6.12	ν_{yz}	0.39	G_{yz}	1.99	S_z	118	S_z	1176	CTE_z	78.42

For the purposes of this work the material creep and stress relaxation characteristics were required. Since creep is strongly dependent on temperature, stress relaxation testing of CSM laminates was carried out at different temperatures and at different initial strains. The temperatures ranged from room temperature (25°C) up to the post-cure temperature of 80°C. Stress relaxation times were found to be short and each test was completed in less than 24 hours. Fig. 1 shows typical stress relaxation curves obtained for a CSM-vinyl ester laminate. The data was formulated into a number of Kelvin models connected in series. These models

were than incorporated into the subsequent non-linear time dependent FEM analysis, by introducing creep strains as internal forces. [8].

Fig. 1: Stress relaxation of post-cured laminates at different temperatures and initial stresses.

SOFTWARE DEVELOPMENT

Commercial packages are not designed to take into account effects such as stage lamination, and shrinkages due to cross-polymerisation. As a result, post-cure shrinkages are simulated as strain change due to thermal expansions [1]. Non-linear relaxation processes prevent the use of superposition. The effects of thermal expansion and shrinkage cannot thus be calculated independently and then added. For this reason a non-linear finite element code was developed. The code is based on the use of two-dimensional nine-noded axisymmetric elements and allows for simulation of the stage manufacturing process of the flange, as well as the effects of creep and stress relaxation in the resin during post-cure to be properly evaluated.

LINEAR ANALYSES

The flange was modelled using the physical dimensions as determined by Whitfield [1]. These dimensions are shown schematically in Fig.2. Two dimensional axisymmetric elements were used. Care was taken to ensure that the change in direction of the material from the flange face to the pipe was properly modelled.

Fig. 2: Physical dimensions of the flange [mm].

A linear analysis was performed for each of three effects; chemically based cure-shrinkage, thermal shrinkage on cooling from 80°C to room temperature and stage lamination. Simulation of chemically based cure-shrinkage was achieved using standard techniques used to evaluate thermal shrinkage. The simulation of the development of residual stresses due to the five-stage lamination was completed in six steps. Initially it was assumed that the first stage became fixed to the mould. The next four steps involved the subsequent placement of each of the stages. As the stages were applied it was assumed that each new stage shrinks over the previously applied stage. Shrinkage was based on the properties listed in Table 1. The post-curing effect due to the exotherm on previously cured layers was ignored due to the unavailability of data concerning this phenomenon. The sixth step simulated the removal of the flange from the mould. This was accomplished by removing the appropriate boundary conditions.

The stress and strain results for the cases of chemically based cure-shrinkage, thermal shrinkage on cooling from 80°C to room temperature and stage lamination are shown in Fig.'s 3 - 5 respectively. In these figures, "In Plane" stresses and strains refer to direct stresses and strains in the plane of the model and aligned with the local direction of the material. "Hoop" stresses and strains refer to direct stresses and strains in the circumferential direction. "Through Thickness" stresses and strains refer to direct stresses and strains normal to the local material plane. The spring-back deflections are given in Table 2.

Since these results are based on the use of a linear analysis, the results for a post-cured flange manufactured using stage lamination was simply obtained by the use of superposition of the three sets of results.

Fig. 3: Stresses and strains arising from linear analysis of chemically based cure-shrinkage.

Fig. 4: Stresses and strains arising from linear analysis of thermal shrinkage.

Fig. 5: Stresses and strains arising from a linear analysis the stage lamination technique.

Table 2: Comparison between different spring-back results

Method of analysis	Spring back [mm]
Physically measured after room temperature cure [5]	0.03
Physically measured after post-cure [5]	0.13
Linear analysis – Chemically based contraction	0.0046
Linear analysis – Thermal contraction	0.0554
Linear analysis – Stage lamination	0.0040
Total spring back – Using superposition	0.0640

NON-LINEAR ANALYSIS

It is frequently assumed that at post-cure temperature all the residual stresses within the laminate become insignificant [6]. The consequence of this assumption is that thermal contraction effectively becomes the sole source of residual stresses. A linear analysis of this situation gives spring-back results as seen in Table 2 that are insufficient to be the root of the measured spring back. The material, however, experiences non-linear processes such as creep or stress relaxation during cooling from the post cure temperature. This effect is considered in the following non-linear analysis.

For the purposes of the non-linear analysis, the assumption that stresses due to initial cure relax and become insignificantly small at post-cure temperatures was made. The time dependant nature of the material during cooling is modelled through the use of a series of iterations similar to those described in Ref. [8]. The temperature distribution through the thickness of the flange was determined after assuming that the surface of the flange cools

down from the post cure temperature to room temperature in 15 minutes. The thermal conductivity constants were based on theoretical values.

The method relies on first analysing the temperature distribution within the laminate at short intervals. At each interval the temperature dependent creep properties were evaluated for each element and changes due to creep were evaluated during this interval. Creep effects as well as post-cure shrinkages for the time interval were then added as internal forces and the resulting displacements calculated. The temperature distribution during the next time interval was then determined and the above process was repeated until the flange was cooled to room temperature and all creep and relaxation effects became insignificant.

The stress and strain results for this analysis are shown in Fig. 6. The spring-back deflection is given in Table 3.

Fig. 6: Stress and strain distributions resulting from a non-linear analysis of cooling.

Table 3: Comparison between different spring back results

Method of analysis	Spring back [mm]
Non-Linear analysis – Thermal contraction	0.0179

DISCUSSION

It is seen from the linear analyses that thermal effects are significantly larger than those caused by either chemically-based cure shrinkage or stage lamination. The most significant tensile stresses correspond to circumferential stresses on the inner face of the pipe section and through-thickness stresses in the “corner” region of the flange. The latter clearly arise from the constraints imposed by the double curvature in this region. The measured spring-back of

the flange is poorly predicted by the use of a linear analysis. The spring-back predicted by thermal effects is only approximately 43% of the measured value. Even using superposition of thermal effects, chemically-based shrinkage effects and the effects of stage lamination, the predicted spring-back is still less than 50% of the measured value.

The use of a non-linear analysis based on thermal effects in no way improves the situation. In this case, the spring-back predicted by thermal effects reduces to only approximately 14% of the measured value. It appears that the accuracy of the non-linear technique is limited by assuming that creep effects reduce residual stress at elevated post-cure temperatures down to insignificant values.

It has been shown [9] that on a microscale, the stresses in the matrix near the fibre interface are orders of magnitude higher than those used in the creep evaluation in this work. Furthermore these stresses do not decay to insignificant values at post cure temperatures. Lange [10] showed that stress build-up during initial cure can vary from less than 1% of the total stress in lightly cross linked epoxy to more than 30% in highly cross linked epoxies and acrylates. It appears that these effects need to be included into a representative analysis if spring-back effects are to be properly modelled.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Linear FEM analysis of spring-back in pipe flanges does not yield good predictions.

The assumption that stresses decay to insignificant values at post-cure temperatures does not appear to be appropriate for the analysis of spring-back in pipe-flanges.

The use of bulk relaxation data does not appear to be appropriate for the analysis of spring-back in pipe-flanges.

Further work using non-linear techniques that take account of micro-scale stresses is required.

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